

SCANDINAVIAN WALKING AS THE MAIN MEANS OF PRESERVING AND STRENGTHENING THE HEALTH OF THE POPULATION

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Abstract: This article spoke about the importance of using the Scandinavian walking sport through new innovative digital technologists in improving the health, rehabilitation, physical fitness level and prolonging the average life age of all segments of the population.

Keywords: physical culture and sports, skeletal muscles, health improvement of the population, Scandinavian walking, measuring instruments, means of control, monitoring, introduction, control, complex, methodology.

СКАНДИНАВСКАЯ ХОДЬБА КАК ОСНОВНОЕ СРЕДСТВО СОХРАНЕНИЯ И УКРЕПЛЕНИЯ ЗДОРОВЬЯ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ

Аннотация: В данной статье говорилось о важности использования скандинавской ходьбы посредством новых инновационных цифровых технологий в улучшении здоровья, реабилитации, уровня физической подготовленности и продлении среднего возраста жизни всех слоев населения.

Ключевые слова: физическая культура и спорт, скелетные мышцы, оздоровление населения, скандинавская ходьба, средства измерения, средства контроля, мониторинг, внедрение, контроль, комплекс, методика.

ACTUALITY

In our society, large-scale work is carried out aimed at the formation of a healthy lifestyle, the creation of conditions in accordance with the requirements of the time for the regular participation of the population, especially the younger generation in physical education and mass sports, the maintenance of health of kholda ahali, increasing the level of physical fitness, the prevention and rehabilitation of overweight, cardiovascular diseases In particular, the development of Science in the Republic of Uzbekistan, conducting scientific research in every field and practical implementation of the obtained scientific results, are today considered as priorities of state policy. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 "Strategy of actions on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021", Resolution No. PD-3907 of August 14, 2018 "On measures to bring up young people spiritually, morally and physically fit, to raise their education system to a qualitatively new level", The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-5538 dated September 5, 2018 "On additional measures to improve the management system of public education" shows the high attention paid to the development of physical culture and sports, especially among young people. [1,2]

The study and analysis of scientific and methodological literature of local and foreign scientists shows that there are many scientific studies devoted to the problems of physical education in the field of Health Promotion, in particular, G.V.Julin, I.A.Koshbakhtiev, D.D.Sharipov, L.I.Lubishov, T.S.Usmankhodzhaev and others.

Problems of Organization of physical education classes in the direction of Health Improvement M.V.Zvereva, A.M.Kazin, L.V.Smuriga, I.A.Sennikova, A.G.O'edrin, T.A.Daminova, B.T.Khalmatova and others.

To analyze the age characteristics in the physical preparation of Primary School students O.V.Goncharova, V.I.Lyax, V.A.Ermakov, A.N.Kainav, T.G.Sulimova, A.No, it's not.Farrahova, I.G.Dukalsky, V.P.Guba, A.A.It was carried out on the basis of the works of gujalovsky and others. [3,4]

The aim of the research work: Walking all layers of morality in the Scandinavian way consists in improving the level of development and preparation of kholda kharmonic, which uses computer and mobile applications.

The following are the scientific novelty of the study:

Conducting health-improving activities and maintaining the level of Health, morphofunctional state and physical fitness of the population.

Justification of the methodology for using Scandinavian walking aids in maintaining and strengthening the health of the population.

Development of a Scandinavian classification of walking tools, depending on the influence of the development of physical qualities.

Improving the effectiveness of physical and functional training indicators on the carpet using Scandinavian walking with all layers of the population of our country.

RESEARCH METHODS

Analysis and generalization of scientific and methodological literature; pedagogical test; medical and biological methods; pedagogical experiment; methods of mathematical Statistics.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND ITS DISCUSSION

Scandinavian walking (walking with a stick, Nordic walking, Finnish walking) is a simple, that is, a typical walk, for which specially designed sticks will help us. Walking in the Scandinavian method is the most effective and safe type of physical activity, and it is one of the sports that is of great help in maintaining the overall development and health of all segments of the population. In school, college, university and all educational institutions, students must disclose their abilities not only mentally, but also physically. At the same time, due to the fact that most people are misty with a lot of mental cocktails, a decrease in the level of the nervous system, imunity, occurs to cardiovascular diseases in the ham.

In such conditions, walking in the Scandinavian way is the only opportunity to strengthen health and help the young organism develop comprehensively. In axoli's free time, Scandinavian style walking training is as useful as possible, comfortable and safe as it stands out from bashqa sports.

Scandinavian walking fully complies with the criteria listed above. Another convenient aspect of Scandinavian walking is that it is very easy to master. Walking in Scandinavia has a positive effect on the nervous system: it helps to develop hormones such as yendorfin, dopamine and serotonin, preventing stress and depression. Regular fogging with Scandinavian walking leads to memory impairment. As a result, walking exercises with a stick can have a positive effect on the physical relaxation process of mistletoe. [5]

Nordic walking is very easy: the reader walks in a comfortable position and at the same time actively harnesses the sticks. The movements are performed without much effort, and this leads to the fact that 90% of the body's muscles work and 46% more calories are spent than regular

movements. As a result – endurance develops-the mood rises, students begin to enjoy their actions- this is a sign that the brain is saturated with oxygen.

Scandinavian walking lessons have a positive effect on all systems of the human body and are completely safe. The Walk has always been studied, and more than 400 scientific papers have been published on the positive effects of Scandinavian walking today. In the following information, the sleeve important useful aspects of Scandinavian walking are mentioned:

- When walking Scandinavian, the consumption of yenergy is spent by 46% more than when walking normally fast
- Cardiovascular system activity improves by 22%
- 90% of human muscles come to ruin during Scandinavian walking
- Regular fogging with Nordic walking can help reduce neck and back pain.
- walking with a stick reduces the load on the knees and feet compared to conventional walking in the usual case;
- Walking in Scandinavia increases the formation of" positive "hormones (happiness, joy and pleasure), prevents and reduces the production of" negative " hormones;
- Walking in Scandinavia increases stress resistance and improves the condition of people with mental disorders. [2.4]

Therefore, the use of walking in the Scandinavian way in axolini's free time can have an effective effect. The main advantages of performing a Scandinavian walk in a general training plan are:

- * Scandinavian that is, the effectiveness of walking with sticks has been proven

It is known that when walking in Scandinavia, the consumption of yenergy increases by 46% compared to the usual fast walking. This means that those who walk with sticks increase patience, the body has good resistance to diseases; the condition of the body as a whole improves. Walking in Scandinavia is a kind of therapy for diseases of the heart and musculoskeletal system, as well as a sleeve in the fight against overweight, depression in adolescence is an effective way.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of a study on the use of Scandinavian walking in the free time of all layers of Axoli made it possible to note the following conclusions:

1. According to the results of the study and analysis of scientific methodological literature, it was found that today this Scandinavian walk is used by adult people to improve their health. A lack of literature based on sufficient scientific research on the physical development of children and the level of training was found in the research process.
2. Scandinavian walking in the all-round development of children makes them have a positive effect on their body. There is hardly any jarocal cartilage in the training jarocons. Scandinavian walking provides muscle performance (up to 90%) compared to Odii walking. The whole body is able to participate in the movement, the active functioning of the vital muscles of the legs, abdomen, buttocks, back and arms of the sleeve was observed to be ensured at the same time.
4. This situation determines the need and relevance of developing a methodology for classes using Scandinavian walking tools, taking into account the climatic and geographical features of our country. These results serve to improve the health of akholi, improve physical development and increase the level of physical fitness.

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